

ETHNIC ASPECTS OF THE MIGRATION POLICY OF THE RUSSIAN EMPIRE IN WESTERN KAZAKHSTAN (1860S – EARLY 20TH CENTURY)

*Sarsembayev A.
Kazakhstan*

Abstract

This article reveals the content and specifics of the resettlement policy of the Russian Empire in the territory of Western Kazakhstan in the period from 1868 to 1917. A comprehensive analysis of the nature of the resettlement movement is carried out, the main stages, trends and directions of migration processes, mainly affecting the Russian and Ukrainian population, are determined. Particular attention is paid to the goals and objectives of the imperial migration policy, as well as its impact on the ethnic structure and demographic dynamics of the region. Administratively, the following administrative-territorial units belonged to the studied region during the specified period: 1) Gurevsky, Lbishchensky, Temirsky and Uralsky districts of the Uralsk region; 2) Aktobe and Irgiz districts of the Turgai region; 3) Bukeevsky district of the Astrakhan province; 4) Mangyshlak district of the Transcaspian region. Migration flows to the region were mainly formed from the provinces of the European part of the Russian Empire, which predetermined the ethnic and ethno-confessional composition of the settlers. Based on a wide range of sources - including archival documents, statistical data and ethnographic materials - the features of the colonial policy of the empire are revealed, in particular, the process of confiscating lands from the indigenous Kazakh nomadic population and their subsequent redistribution in favor of East Slavic settlers. The migration movement of the late 19th - early 20th centuries is considered one of the key factors that had a significant impact on the transformations in the ethno-demographic development of the Kazakh people.

Keywords: Western Kazakhstan, resettlement policy, Kazakhs, East Slavic ethnic groups, land seizures, Turgay-Ural resettlement region, ethnodemographic processes.

Main part

It is known that the end of the 19th – beginning of the 20th century is one of the key stages in the history of the Kazakh people. This period was marked by the beginning of a profound socio-economic and cultural transformation. The resettlement policy of tsarist Russia significantly exacerbated the existing social contradictions in Kazakh society, contributed to the intensification of the processes of mass stratification in the aul, and also aggravated political and interethnic conflicts in the region. The resettlement policy of the Russian Empire in Kazakhstan consists of three main periods: 1) 1861–1880s – the period during which the resettlement of peasants was officially prohibited, and it was carried out mainly in the form of spontaneous, unorganized and unauthorized movement of peasants from the central regions of Russia; 2) 1880s – 1906 – the stage at which resettlement became legally permitted, but was not encouraged by government agencies; 3) since 1906 – a period of active state support for the resettlement movement, when it became an integral part of the agrarian reform of P.A. Stolypin, implemented after the First Russian Revolution.

The abolition of serfdom in 1861 created conditions for mass peasant resettlement to the eastern outskirts of the empire. Already in the 1860s, the process of migration of peasants to Kazakhstan from the central regions of Russia began. The resettlement policy in this context was considered by the government as a means of resolving the growing agrarian crisis in the European part of the empire.

Settlers began arriving in Western Kazakhstan in the 1870s. In 1874, the Orenburg Governor-General instructed the military governors of the Ural and Turgai regions to consider the advisability of colonizing the Kazakh steppe. As an initial stage, it was proposed to begin development with cities and suburbs where the

Russian population already lived, which, in the opinion of the authorities, facilitated the process of adaptation and administrative management of the new wave of migrants [1, pp. 118-119].

Basically, peasant migrants settled in the northern regions of the Ural and Turgai regions - there were more fertile lands and it was possible to engage in agriculture and cattle breeding. This trend continued in subsequent years. The southern districts of the Ural region - Gurevsky and Temirsky, as well as the Turgai region - Irgizsky were sparsely populated by migrants. The Mangyshlak district and the Inner Horde were practically not affected by the migration movement. There were arid, semi-desert areas here, which hindered the development of agriculture.

In 1869, the Ak-Tyube fortification was founded. At that time, several peasant families settled near the fortress; they rented land from the Kazakhs. In 1886, there were already 177 families of settlers in the Aktyubinsk district.

The number of residents of Ak-Tyube increased from 397 people in 1881 to 1903 people in 1894. In other areas, the population grew relatively slowly. The population of the city of Irgiz was 925 people in 1870, and 1866 people in 1894. The most active settlement of the Turgai region began only at the beginning of the 20th century [2, p. 105, pp. 115-116].

In the Ural region, land plots were not allocated to peasants, and agricultural settlers, as so-called non-residents, settled on the lands of the Ural Cossack army (in those years there were 51.3 thousand of them). Settlement settlements arose on the rivers Uil, Temir and on the Caspian Sea – Shipovsky settlement, Zhilaya Kosa, etc. But these were not agricultural settlements. The allocation of land to settlers began only in 1886 [2, p.162].

On August 5, 1886, the Embensky district chief reported that 43 families had settled there. In the same year of 1886, the settlement of the Uilsky fortification also began. There were 40 families here – a total of 340 souls of both sexes. The first unauthorized settlement was formed in the Uralsky district in 1890 on the territory of the Dzhirenkupinskaya volost. The resettlement began back in 1887, when two families of tenants first settled here. In 1893, there were 11 households living here, renting 60 dessiatines of land from the Kazakhs. At that time, they turned to the military governor of the region with a request to assign them to the volost, to allocate them land or to lease them a plot for a period of 15 years. Under pressure and arbitrariness of the district and regional authorities, a decision was made in 1896 to allocate a plot of 300 dessiatines to 52 households of this volost for 3 years. And in three years, from 1896 to 1899, about 300 families arrived here. Subsequently, the issue of their eviction and return of lands was not even considered by the official authorities.

The history of the formation of the first large settlement shows that the resettlement took place unauthorizedly and in violation of existing laws. The attitude of local authorities to this process began to change as the influx of peasants increased. As a result, unauthorized settlement of other Kazakh volosts began.

Soon after the formation of the Dzhirenkupinsky settlement, unauthorized settlement of other volosts located along the Ilel and Ural rivers began. By 1899, three more unauthorized settlements with a population had been formed: Chilik - 53 families, Karachaganak - 42 and Burlin - 27 families.

The second stage of resettlement differed from the first by the active participation of the state in the preparation and implementation of this campaign. The abolition of serfdom did not solve the agrarian issue, so the tsarist government, in order to relieve social tension in the country and further colonize Kazakhstan, activated the resettlement policy. The lands of the local nomadic and semi-nomadic population were confiscated for the resettlers in Kazakhstan. The formal basis for this was the decision of the tsarist government in 1868 that all nomadic lands were declared the property of the state and therefore confiscated to the fund of the Resettlement Administration.

In 1881, the "Temporary Rules on the Resettlement of Peasants to Free State Lands" were introduced, according to which peasants received the right to resettle to the outskirts of the empire with the permission of the relevant authorities [3, p. 204]. On March 25, 1891, the Steppe Regulations were adopted, in the section "Land Structure" of which the procedure for resettlement was set out (Articles 119-136). According to the Steppe Regulations, Kazakh lands finally became state property. Thus, Article 119 determined that "the lands occupied by nomads and all the accessories of these lands, including forests ... are recognized as state property." It also stated that the lands of nomads may "become redundant" and be transferred "to the jurisdiction of the Ministry of State Property" [4, p. 395-396].

In December 1896, the Resettlement Directorate was established as part of the Ministry of Internal Affairs. It was engaged in issuing permits for resettlement,

supervised the movement and settlement of settlers, and also made attempts to improve migration legislation [3, p. 204].

Work began on developing a methodology for calculating Kyrgyz land use standards and identifying "surplus" land. Initially, this work was based on the idea of the irrationality of using the vast steppe expanses by nomads, the low profitability of nomadic livestock farming, and the archaic lifestyle of the Kazakhs.

For this purpose, a survey of the land fund of Kazakhstan began under the leadership of statistician F.A. Shcherbina. He led a special expedition to study the steppe regions. The work of this expedition began in 1896 and continued until 1901. The expedition surveyed 171,200 Kazakh and 8,475 Russian farms in 12 districts of the Akmola, Semipalatinsk, and Turgai regions [5, p. 756]. With the establishment of a land norm of 24 units of livestock, translated into horses per farm, in the surveyed districts of the steppe regions, it was proposed to leave 17 million dessiatines of land for 106 thousand Kazakh farms, and the resulting "surplus" – more than 18 million dessiatines – to be transferred to the resettlement fund [6, p. 53].

Thus, arbitrary norms that did not correspond to the actual needs of livestock farming became the starting point for determining the land "surplus" of the Kazakh population and transferring it to the colonization fund. Which inevitably led to the aggravation of social contradictions in the Kazakh steppe, since the confiscation of land from nomads objectively led to a reduction in migrations and a crisis in livestock farming. In 1904-1906, the tsarist government divided the territory of Kazakhstan into four resettlement regions: Turgay-Ural, Akmola, Semipalatinsk and Syr Darya. The resettlement departments that were formed in each such region were charged with identifying new "surplus" lands to create a "resettlement fund". The department also dealt with issues of resettling peasants and supervised the work on preparing land plots, confiscated land from the nomadic Kazakh population, was in charge of the movement of peasants within the resettlement area, and also dealt with all financial issues related to the resettlement matter.

The formation of resettlement plots was carried out in four fertile districts of the Uralsk and Turgai regions without any concern for the interests of nomads from other volosts, districts and regions, which was equivalent to depriving them of the use of land in general. After all, it often happened that the territory of one volost was actually in the communal use of Kazakhs from other volosts. The slightest seizure of a piece of convenient land with natural irrigation in one volost painfully affected the Kazakhs of other districts or regions.

For example, the area of the Uralsk district and the northern part of the Temir district was in the joint communal use of both the settled Kazakhs of the volosts of these two districts, and the nomadic Kazakhs of 17 volosts of the Guryevsky district, 7 southern volosts of the Temir district, 11 volosts of the Mangyshlak and Krasnovodsk districts of the Transcaspian region, a total of 35 nomads. With the beginning of spring, every year

the Kazakhs of these 35 volosts migrated to the borders of the Uralsk district and the northern part of the Temir district and remained here with their herds until late autumn. In late autumn, they migrated from their summer camps to the places of their administrative registration. Thus, the Uralsk and Temir districts were in the use not only of the settled Kazakhs of 21 volosts, but also of the nomadic Kazakhs of 35 volosts. Therefore, the seizure of land for resettlement plots in these districts could seriously affect the nomadic Kazakhs [7, p. 125-127].

From 1893 to 1905, 4,074,180 dessiatines of land were seized in the steppe regions, of which 1,024,412 dessiatines were in the Turgay-Ural region. As a result of the accelerated land management work, the Kazakhs lost 28% of their pre-reform territories [8, p. 47].

As a result of the resettlement policy in 1870-1896, 60,867 people arrived in the Ural region, and 31,459 people in Turgay, or 22.7% of the total number of those who arrived in Kazakhstan [9, p. 65].

The population of Western Kazakhstan increased in 1870-1897. by 442.7 thousand people, or 61.2%. The main ethnic group was still the indigenous population - Kazakhs, whose number increased by 325.3 thousand people, and the share in the region was overwhelming - 82.1%. At the same time, there is a slight decrease in the Kazakh population in relative terms by 5.4%. Next in terms of numbers in the population structure are Russians, who made up 15.4%. At the same time, the growth of the Russian population was very high - more than 2 times. However, the fastest rate of increase was observed in the number of other foreign national groups - 10 times. Thus, the process of forming a multinational composition of the population of Western Kazakhstan began.

The sources of ethnodemographic development changed. If before the 1870s the population growth was mainly due to natural increase, then in the following years the level of migration flows began to increase, expressed in the resettlement of Russian-Ukrainian peasants here. The main flow was from neighboring Russian provinces and partly from Ukraine. But the resettlement did not yet have a significant impact on the change in the nature of demographic processes [10, p. 151]. According to the data in Table 1, from 1878 to 1896, the number of Kazakhs in the Ural region fell twice. The reasons for these processes are rooted in the instability of the life of the Kazakhs, caused by increased dependence on external factors, the instability of nomadic economy. Unfavorable stages in demographic development occurred during the jutes of 1879-1880 and 1891. There is a close relationship between the level of development of nomadic cattle breeding, which is completely dependent on natural conditions, and the rate of population growth, when the violation of the fragile balance is reflected in the total population. The Kazakhs almost always successfully coped with jutes, and they did not have such detrimental consequences for the population before. This was explained by the full observance of the entire production cycle of nomadic cattle breeding, namely, full-fledged summer grazing of cattle, which fattened up enough fat for wintering. But the expulsion of the Kazakhs from the northern lands of the region, where the main summer pastures of the clans were located, led to a violation of the established and vital order, and increased the dependence of the economy on natural fluctuations. Therefore, in the second half of the 19th century, when the process of transferring lands to settlers began, unfavorable demographic trends were observed [10, pp. 148-149].

Table 1.

Change in the number of Kazakh population in the Ural region

Year	Number of kubitkas	Absolute annual growth, +/-
1878	82390	-
1881	82462	+127
1884	77633	-1620
1887	80942	+1104
1890	82000	+343
1893	78362	-1123
1896	81353	+907

[12, pp. 148-149]

A new course of resettlement policy began in the 20th century. The aggravation of the agrarian issue during the revolutionary events of 1905-1907 led to the apogee of the colonial-conquering land policy. The government saw in the peasant resettlement an opportunity to rid the European part of Russia of the rural poor. The resettlement was supposed to distract the attention of land-poor peasants from the landlords' lands. In addition, the resettlement was used for the purpose of Russification of the outskirts of the empire. The resettlement movement to Western Kazakhstan especially unfolded in 1906-1915. Mass agrarian colonization of the territory of Kazakhstan was carried out during the years of the Stolypin agrarian reform, the purpose of which was to eliminate peasant landlessness in Russia and

smooth out the revolutionary movement by mass resettlement of the poorest strata of the peasantry to the east. At the same time, other goals were also pursued: the creation of a political support on the national outskirts from wealthy settlers. In 1907, Stolypin convened a special interdepartmental conference on the land management of the Kazakhs to develop the basic principles of land policy in Kazakhstan. The main objective of the conference was to find the necessary funds to carry out large-scale seizures of Kazakh lands in order to increase the resettlement fund [11, p. 69].

The Director of the Department of Agriculture N.A. Kryukov, speaking at the conference, stated that the same policy should be pursued with respect to the Kazakhs as the Americans were pursuing with respect

to the Indians, driving the latter from their lands to desert areas. Kryukov believed that the implementation of the resettlement policy was hindered by the “nomadic way of life of the foreigners, therefore this obstacle must be put an end to” [7, pp. 115-116].

The land provision standards established by Shcherbina's expedition were, in the opinion of the conference, outdated, therefore new, reduced standards should be established [7, p. 49]. New expeditions were organized that could substantiate the need for a sharp reduction in these standards.

In 1904-1912, under the leadership of P.P. Khvorostansky, statistical studies were conducted in several districts of Western Kazakhstan: Irgiz, Ural, Temir, and Aktyubinsk. In the Ural region, 929,132 dessiatines of "surplus" were determined, and in the Turgai region, 1,682,357 dessiatines [12, p. 261].

The materials of the new expeditions contained the conclusion that the land standards of Shcherbina's expeditions were overstated, and that the nomadic Kazakhs did not need large spaces, since they were everywhere moving toward a settled way of life and agriculture. As a result, if according to the Shcherbina expedition, the minimum land use standards for Kazakh farms, depending on the region and other conditions, were 110-209 dessiatines, and the maximum 187-510 dessiatines, then according to the data of the repeated expeditions of 1904-1908, they became 70-125 dessiatines and 119-219 dessiatines, respectively. Thus, the decrease was from 36-40% to 36-57%. In 1910, Stolypin and the chief manager of land management and agriculture Krivoshein made an inspection trip to Siberia, the Steppe Region and the Volga region. The conclusions drawn by the ministers and dedicated to the results of the trip boiled down to the need for land management "not for the Kirghiz, but for the Kirghiz steppe itself." The future of the Kazakh population was to consist of its gradual eviction from lands suitable for agriculture to the south, to lands “less fertile, but rewarding them with large expanses of land” [13, p.92-93]. The resettlement department sought to select arable lands

first and foremost for the colonization fund. Resettlement plots were usually created on the arable lands of Kazakh auls. The confiscation of water sources also had very serious consequences. Forests were also withdrawn from the use of the local population, becoming the “sole property of the treasury.” The forestry department often “found” forests where they actually did not exist. The main goal of the foresters was to confiscate as much land as possible for summer cottages in a short period of time [14, p.52].

The plundering of Kazakh lands, forests, and water sources was accompanied in many cases by the displacement of settled Kazakh auls from their inhabited territories, the demolition of mosques, the demarcation of cemeteries into resettlement areas, and the demolition of winter huts. The population had to move to new places. Sometimes the matter was not limited to a single displacement. Before the Kazakhs evicted from their lands and winter huts had time to settle in new places, those responsible for the work found that the area confiscated from them was not large enough, and a new confiscation followed. Such displacements of the same aul were sometimes carried out 2-3 times. As an example, in 1908 a complaint was sent to the Resettlement Administration about the formation of areas on lands where 58 Kazakh tents were already standing (Tulaganai area, Temirovsky district) [15]. In total, in the Turgai-Ural resettlement region, according to the results of the Stolypin colonization program for 1906-1915, 4,378,046 dessiatines of land were seized, and 1,216 resettlement plots were formed [16, p. 30].

Since the main flow of settlers was directed to the most fertile lands, as a result of this, the land area of the nomadic cattle breeding economy was noticeably narrowed, which was deprived of the best wintering and summer pastures, and the conditions for the development of agricultural economy of the Kazakh population were eliminated.

The most intensive period of resettlement falls on 1906-1911. Table 2 shows the intensity of migration by year.

Table 2.

Migration to the Turgai-Ural resettlement region, 1906-1915

Year	The number of settlers arrived		
	Ural and Turgai regions		Total arrived in Kazakhstan
	Abs.	%	
1906	6000	23,9	25100
1907	46209	57,5	80360
1908	16337	20,4	80157
1909	29234	33,3	87711
1910	33696	50,2	67097
1911	32158	43,5	73994
1912	12937	31,5	41077
1913	18631	37,5	50291
1914	19160	35,9	53360
1915	6746	31,5	21440
Всего:	221108	38,1	580587

[15, c.144-145].

If we trace the dynamics of the number of migrants by year, we can see that the very first year after the issuance of the decree of 1906 gave a huge surge. In

1906, 6,000 males arrived in the Turgay-Uralsky district, and in 1907 already 46,209 people. The level of resettlement decreases and increases in waves, and by

1915 it falls to 6,746 people. In the Turgay region, Aktyubinsk district was mainly populated. 15 settlements were created here. In the Aktyubinsk district in 1907-1912, 109.6 thousand people arrived, and in 1907 alone 42.2 thousand migrants arrived here. In total for 1897-1915. In 1903, 112.5 thousand people moved to the Aktobe and Irgiz districts, of which 110.1 thousand moved to the Aktobe district. In the entire West Kazakhstan region, the highest proportion of migrants was recorded here - they made up 45.4% of the total population of this district [10, p. 159].

In another part of the region, in the Ural region, the preparation of resettlement sites was completed by 1903. From this moment on, the period of the most active settlement began. The division of resettlement sites began with the Ural and Temir districts. In 1906-1910, 47,018 people were settled here, for whom 102 plots of land with a total area of over 638 thousand dessiatines were allocated. The scale of the resettlement is evidenced by the excess of the rate of migration influx of settlers over the level of natural increase of Kazakhs by 2.5 times. Of the total number of settlers, 40,211 people (85.5%) settled in the Uralsky district, 8,366 people (17.7%) in Temirsky and 2,225 people (4.7%) in Gurevsky. There were no settlers in the Lbishchensky district, but the number of non-residents increased sharply here, which is explained by the resettlement of those who arrived in the territory of the Cossack lands [10, p. 160]. In 1910-1915, more than 38 thousand people moved to the Uralsky district [18, p. 9]. In the Mangyshlaksy district of the Transcaspian region, settlers populated coastal fishing areas. Fishing villages were founded in this region. By 1910, only 1,615 people lived in 3 villages [19, p. 353, 369, 388]. The growth was largely due to an increase in the sedentary population: by 290 thousand in the Turgai region, by 120 thousand in the Ural region. The constantly high level of growth, which occurred mainly as a result of an influx from outside, is clearly visible. That is, the sedentary population did not experience demographic shocks during the years of migration. An increase in natural growth is noted.

The nomadic population in both regions had approximately the same conditions for farming, but the level of natural growth was not the same. In the Turgai region, the nomadic population increased by 88 thousand people. The situation is different in the Ural region - over 14 years, the total number increased by only 31.8

thousand people. The decrease in rates is explained by a sharp drop in natural growth, an excess of mortality over the birth rate [10, pp. 164-165].

The 1897 census recorded the number of Kazakhs in the Uralsk district as 150.9 thousand people, which was 51.3% of the total population of the district. It subsequently decreased - in 1903 to 72.6 thousand, and in 1913 it was already 77.3 thousand people. At the same time, the specific weight decreased to 23.9%. In parallel with the decrease in the number of Kazakhs, there was a general decrease in the population of the Uralsk district during this period from 293.6 thousand to 289.2 thousand people. Between 1897 and 1917, the ratio of the main ethnic groups changed dramatically. The number of Russians increased from 124.1 thousand to 237 thousand people, or almost 2 times, amounting to 74%. The number of other ethnic groups increased. The only ethnic group whose numbers decreased over these years were the Kazakhs. They decreased by 48.7%. The Kazakhs, who were the main, largest group in the population of the district, became an ethnic minority over these 20 years. The proportion of Kazakhs in the Turgai region fell by 31.04%, in the Uralsk region by 15.73% [2, p. 178].

In general, the number of Kazakhs decreased not only in the Uralsk, but also in the Lbishchensky district, amounting to 84.5 thousand people together. At the same time, an increase in the Kazakh population was noted in the Gurevsky district by 177%, in Temirsky by 155%, in Bukeyevsky by 159% and in Mangyshlak by 113%. In total, the growth of the Kazakh population over these 4 years in these lands amounted to 236.9 thousand people. The increase in the number of Kazakhs in the more southern districts occurred as a result of their outflow from the neighboring districts - Uralsky and Lbishchensky.

The reason for the mass exodus of the indigenous population during this period was the forced expulsion of Kazakhs from the northern part of the region and the confiscation of 700 thousand dessiatines of land from them to create a resettlement land fund and the subsequent placement of settlers here [10, pp. 160-161].

The result was a radical change in the national structure of the Ural region and the region as a whole. The resettlement led to an increase in the Russian and Ukrainian population in 1907-1912 alone by 200 thousand people (table 3).

Table 3.

Dynamics of the number of Kazakhs, Russians and Ukrainians for 1897 – 1915 (thousand people)

Counties	Kazakhs			Russians			Ukrainians		
	1897	1915	growth	1897	1915	growth r	1897	1915	growth r
Ural	150,9	77,6	-73,5	124,0	237,0	+113,0	1,9	4,6	+2,7
Lbishchensk	144,3	133,3	-11,0	21,8	62,6	+40,4	0,5	14,4	+13,9
Gurev	70,9	125,0	+54,1	14,7	37,1	+21,4	-	-	-
Temir	94,1	146,0	+51,9	0,3	22,9	+22,6	-	6,8	+6,8
Inner Horde	207,2	239,5	+122,3	6,6	7,1	+0,4	-	-	-
Mangyshlak	63,8	72,4	+8,6	3,8	4,5	+0,7	-	-	-
Aktobe	109,6	126,9	+17,3	3,2	52,6	+49,4	1,0	57,5	+56,5
Irgiz	97,1	117,3	+20,2	0,9	2,2	+1,3	-	0,2	+0,2
Total	937,9	1128,0	+190,1	175,3	426,0	+250,7	3,4	83,5	+80,1

The population of the Turgay and Ural regions by 1914 had doubled compared to 1870, from 807,599 to 1,530,032 people. This was due to a large influx of settlers. In total, 335,292 settlers of both sexes settled in the Turgay and Ural regions from 1870 to 1914 [9, p. 70, 78]. Migration processes at the end of the 19th – beginning of the 20th century contributed to the increase in urban population growth. The urban population was constantly growing. Over 27 years (1870-1897), the growth rate was 1224% in the Turgay region and 214% in the Ural region. The urban population also grew quite intensively in the subsequent period (1897-1914) – by 63%. The growth rate of the urban population was higher than that of the rural population [9, p.73-74].

The least increase in the urban population occurred due to natural growth. The share of the Kazakh population in the cities was insignificant, and industry in them developed slowly. At the same time, the Kazakhs made up the main contingent of the workforce in industrial centers located outside the cities, as well as at railway junctions and stations.

The replenishment of the urban population occurred mainly due to peasant migrants. Some of them officially transferred to the urban classes, some became ordinary people, while remaining in the rank of peasants [9, p.96].

According to the First General Census of 1897, the percentage of natives of other provinces in the non-local population of the Turgai region was especially high - 65.5% of the total urban population.

The majority of the non-local population were people of the rural class. By region, the share of people of rural status, natives of other provinces, living in cities, was: in Turgai - 95%, Ural - 83%.

The resettlement policy of tsarism contributed to the change in the national composition of Kazakhstan - at the beginning of the 20th century, there were more than 60 nationalities in the territory of the region. In the northern regions of the Ural and Turgai regions, the percentage of Russian-speaking population began to increase. In 1914, Russians made up 40.8% of the population in the Ural region, 37.5% of the Turgai region [9, p. 85]. During the period from 1906 to 1915, the number of peasants increased by 83%, the Cossack population - by 21%, Kazakhs - by 6%.

The resettlement policy led to the displacement of the Kazakh population to the south of the region and changed the nature of ethnodemographic development as a whole. Mainly Kazakhs were expelled from their former places of settlement, whose nomadic routes passed through the territory of the Uralsk and Lbishchensk districts. As a result of the resettlement, about 100,000 Kazakhs were deprived of their traditional places of residence. At the same time, a significant part of the Kazakhs settled in the Gurevsky district and the Bukeyevskaya Horde, and their displacement, in turn, caused the displacement of local residents even further to the South. As a result, the Bukeyevskaya Horde, Mangyshlak and Irgiz districts became completely Kazakh. In the Gurevsky district, the Russian and other non-Russian population made up 22.9%, in Temir - 16.9%, in Lbishchen - 35%, in Aktobe 45.4%,

in Uralsk the majority - 75.7%. As a result of the resettlement, the Kazakh population was forced to the south of the region, dominating in the southern and central parts of Western Kazakhstan. The intensified resettlement policy led to negative processes in the demographic development of the indigenous population. The natural increase of the nomadic Kazakhs was not only low, but also inferior to the indicators of the sedentary Kazakh and Russian populations. The deterioration of the material situation in connection with the allocation of the best lands to the settlers, insufficient medical care led to the fact that the Kazakh population grew more slowly than the settler population. If in 1867-1896 the natural increase absolutely prevailed in the overall population growth of the Turgai region, then in 1897-1916 the share of natural and mechanical increase was almost equal, and in 1907-1912 the latter absolutely prevailed [2, p. 162]. And the only ethnic group whose share decreased **were the Kazakhs.**

Findings

Thus, the migration processes that unfolded at the end of the 19th century had a significant impact on the transformation of the ethnic structure of the population of Western Kazakhstan. As a result of the resettlement policy of the Russian Empire, Russians and Ukrainians became the predominant ethnic groups in the region after the indigenous Kazakh population.

The redistribution of land and the definition of land rights for local residents led to the emergence of the so-called "Kyrgyz (Kazakh) question", which became one of the most pressing problems in the context of the mass resettlement of the East Slavic and other European population to the Steppe Region.

The resettlement policy implemented in Kazakhstan at the beginning of the 20th century was a direct reflection of the colonial status of the region and was manifested in the following key trends: 1) strengthening the process of formation of the multiethnic composition of the region's population; 2) a decrease in the share of the indigenous Kazakh population in the overall demographic structure; 3) an increase in the number and share of the European settler population, primarily Russians and Ukrainians; 4) partial growth of cities, accompanied by the predominance of people from various regions of the empire in their population, as well as representatives of social strata closely associated with the colonial administration and entrepreneurial activity.

In general, the resettlement policy of the Russian Empire in Western Kazakhstan played a significant role in changing the ethnodemographic appearance of the region and laid the foundations for subsequent transformations in the social, cultural and political spheres.

References

1. Alekseenko N.V. Population of pre-revolutionary Kazakhstan (number, location, composition, 1870-1914). - Alma-Ata: "Science" Kaz.SSR, 1981. - 112 p.
2. Bekmakhanova N.E. Multinational population of Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan in the era of capitalism (60s of the 19th century – 1917). – M.: Nauka, 1986. – 245 p.
3. Central State Archive of Kazakhstan. F.I-29.I.1.V.1.C.60.S.25-25rev.

4. Friesen D.Ya. Relations between Kazakhs and peasant settlers of Western Kazakhstan in the 19th – early 20th centuries. // Samara Scientific Bulletin. – 2016. – No. 4 (17). – P. 117-122.
5. Materials on the history of the political system of Kazakhstan (from the time of Kazakhstan's accession to Russia until the Great October Socialist Revolution): Collection // Comp. Cand. of Law. Sciences M. G. Masevich. - Vol. 1. - Alma-Ata: Academy of Sciences of the Kazakh SSR, 1960. - 441 p.
6. Materials on the Land Issue in Asian Russia. – Issue 6: Results of the Resettlement Case Beyond the Urals from 1906 to 1915 // Comp. V.A. Tresvyatsky. – Petrograd, 1918. – 41 p.
7. Note by the Chairman of the Council of Ministers and Chief Manager of Land Management and Agriculture on a Trip to Siberia and the Volga Region in 1910: Appendix to the Most Humble Report. – St. Petersburg, 1910. – 172 p.
8. Report on the revision of the Turkestan region, carried out by the highest order by Senator Hofmeister Count K.K. Palen: Resettlement Case in Turkestan. – St. Petersburg: Senate. type., 1910. – 436 p.
9. Resettlement and land management beyond the Urals in 1906-1910 and the Report on resettlement and land management for 1910. - St. Petersburg: Resettlement Administration, 1911. - 501 p.
10. Review of Resettlement and Land Management Beyond the Urals in 1906–1910 // Colonization Issues. – 1912. – No. 10. – Pp. 219-288.
11. Review of the Ural Region for 1915 // Appendix to the Most Submissive Report of the Military Governor. – Uralsk, 1916. – 141 p.
12. Sdykov M.N. History of the population of Western Kazakhstan. - Almaty, 2004. - 408 p.
13. Sedelnikov T.I. The Struggle for Land in the Kirghiz Steppe: (Kirghiz Land Issue and the Government's Colonization Policy). – SPb.: S. Dorovatovsky and A. Charushnikov, 1907. – 79 p.
14. Shakhmatov V. F. Historiography of Kazakhstan // Essays on the history of historical science in the USSR. - Moscow: Publ. Academy of Sciences of the USSR, 1963. - Vol. III. - P. 751-760.
15. Shonanuly T. Zher tagdyry – el tagdyry. – Almaty: Sanat, 1995.–224 p.
16. Soroka N.N. Research of the steppe regions of Kazakhstan in the 80-90s of the XIX century to determine the norms of land provision of the Kazakh population and justify the formation of the resettlement fund // Omsk Scientific Bulletin. - 2009 - No. 2 (76). - P. 50-54.
17. Journal of the Conference on Land Management of the Kirghiz. - St. Petersburg, 1907. - 146 p.
18. Tarasova E.V. The influence of the resettlement movement on land relations in the Steppe Territory and Turkestan in the late 19th – early 20th centuries. // Bulletin of the Altai State University. – 2003 – No. 4/2 (80/2). – P. 203-206.
19. Vaganov O.A. Land Policy of the Tsarist Government in Kazakhstan (1907–1914) // Historical Notes: Collection // Ed. B.D. Grekov. – Moscow: USSR Academy of Sciences, 1950. – Vol. 31. – Pp. 61-87.